

CONDENSATION OF PHENOLS AND PHENOLIC ETHERS WITH ACETONE DICARBOXYLIC ACID. USE OF CONDENSING AGENTS OTHER THAN SULPHURIC ACID. A NEW NON-ACIDIC CONDENSATION PRODUCT

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Resorcin has been condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid in the presence of (i) anhydrous aluminium chloride, (ii) phosphorous oxychloride, (iii) phosphorous pentoxide and (iv) thionyl chloride, as condensing agents. In each case a new non-acidic condensation product has been obtained in addition to the expected 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid. A formula of the dilactone of $\beta\beta$ -di-(2:4-dihydroxyphenyl) glutaric acid has been provisionally suggested for the new compound.

Phenols, naphthols and their ethers have been condensed with β -diketonic esters in the presence of several condensing agents e.g. sulphuric acid (Pechmann and Burton, *Annalen*, 1894, 261, 167), phosphorous oxychloride (Naik, Desai and Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 801), anhydrous aluminium chloride (Shah and Sethna, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228); alcoholic hydrochloric acid (Appel, *ibid.*, 1935, 1031); phosphorus pentoxide (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129); sodium ethoxide (Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*); the main products in almost all cases being coumarins.

Phenols, and their ethers have also been condensed with a β -diketonic acid, acetone dicarboxylic acid. In most of the reactions the condensing agent has been sulphuric acid and the following types of compounds have been obtained :—(1) Coumarin-4-acetic acids (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1608; Limaye, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 158); (2) β -aryl glutaconic acids (Limaye and Bhawe, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 137; Dixit, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 787; Gogte, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1934, 1, 48); (3) $\beta\beta$ -diaryl glutaric acids: *ortho* condensation (Dixit and Gokhale, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1934, 3, 95), *para* condensation (Gogte, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 5A, 535); (4) $\beta\beta$ -diaryl butyric acids (Bokil and Vyas, *Rasayanam*, 1939, 198); (5) hydrindenylidene acetic acids (Limaye and Gogte, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1935, 4, 135).

Phosphorus pentoxide has been used by Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*) to condense resorcin with acetone dicarboxylic acid and he obtained 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid as the product.

Anhydrous aluminium chloride has been used by Bhawe (*Rasayanam*, 1939, 180) to condense acetone dicarboxylic acid with resorcin dimethyl ether, the condensation product being $\beta\beta$ -(2:4-dimethoxyphenylene)-1:5-bis-glutaconic acid.

The present work was undertaken with a view to studying the condensation of phenols and phenolic ethers with acetone dicarboxylic acid in the presence of condensing reagents other than sulphuric acid.

Resorcin has been condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid (1:1 mol.) in the presence of (i) aluminium chloride, (ii) phosphorus oxychloride, (iii) phosphorus pentoxide and (iv) thionyl chloride. In the case of (i) and (iv) carbon disulphide and benzene have been used as solvents respectively while in the remaining two no solvent is used.

In each of these reactions, the crude condensation product could be separated into two parts—(A) an acid, and (B) a non-acid.

The acid (A) on crystallisation from alcohol separates as shining long needles and is identified with 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid by mixed m.p. and conversion into 4-methylumbelliferone. The non-acid (B) crystallises from alcohol in very small prisms blackening at 210° and melting at 290°. An alcoholic solution of the substance gives a greenish black colouration with ferric chloride indicating the presence of free OH groups. It forms neither a phenylhydrazone nor a semicarbazone.

An ebullioscopic determination shows that its molecular weight is in the neighbourhood of 310, thus indicating a condensation between two molecules of resorcin and one of acetone dicarboxylic acid.

An estimation of the OH groups by the acetylation method showed the presence of two free OH groups in the substance.

To arrive at the constitution of this non-acidic substance, it has been subjected to the following reactions :

(1) *Alkaline hydrolysis*.—The substance is hydrolysed by both alcoholic and aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%). In either case, the products of hydrolysis are (i) 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid and (ii) resorcin, which is isolated by converting it into its 4 : 6-dibromo derivative.

(2) *Acidic hydrolysis*.—A solution of the substance in sulphuric acid (75%) is refluxed for a couple of hours. This gives almost quantitative yields of (i) 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid and (ii) resorcin.

(3) *Hydrolysis and methylation* is carried out according to Robertson and Canter (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1875). This gives two products : (i) β -2 : 4-dimethoxyphenylglutamic acid and (ii) resorcin dimethyl ether.

(4) *Oxidation*.—The substance is oxidised by (i) chromic acid, (ii) alkaline potassium permanganate and (iii) hydrogen peroxide (10 vols.) but in none of these reactions could a workable product be separated and in each case nearly 50% of the original substance were recovered unchanged.

(5) *Methylation*.—The substance could not be methylated.

(6) *Acetylation* gives diacetyl derivative (m.p. 186°). An attempt to deacetylate it by heating with sodium hydroxide produces 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid and resorcin.

(7) *Benzoylation* gives a dibenzoyl derivative (m.p. 206°) which on hydrolysis with alkali decomposes to 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid and resorcin.

(8) *Heating at m.p.*—No marked change is effected by heating.

In view of the foregoing results, the formula of dilactone of $\beta\beta$ -di-(2 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaric acid (II, R' = OH ; R'' = H) has been provisionally assigned to the non-acidic condensation product (B).

The reaction between resorcin and acetone dicarboxylic acid can be shown to take place in the following three ways to produce this compound :—

[$\beta\beta$ -di-(2 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaric acid] (I, R = R' = OH ; R'' = H)

Acetone dicarboxylic acid is known to condense in its ketonic form with phenols to give $\beta\beta$ -diaryl glutaric acids (cf. Dixit and Gokhale, *loc. cit.*).

A similar additive reaction between a molecule of *p*-cresol ethyl ether and a molecule of β -(2-ethoxy-5-methylphenyl)-glutaconic acid has been reported by Gogte (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2, 196), the product being $\beta\beta$ -di-(2-ethoxy-5-methylphenyl)-glutaric acid (I, R = OEt ; R' = H ; R'' = Me). This compound changed to (i) the dilactone (II, R' = H ; R'' = Me) under the influence of sulphuric acid (80%) and (ii) to 6-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid (III) on hydrolysis with alkali.

An intermediate monobasic lactonic acid of the type (V) has been mentioned by Gogte (*loc. cit.*) during the conversion of his $\beta\beta$ -di-(2-ethoxy-5-methyl phenyl)-glutaconic acid (I, R = OEt; R' = H; R'' = Me) into the corresponding dilactone (II, R' = H; R'' = Me).

A direct synthesis of the dilactone has, therefore, been attempted by the condensation of resorcin dimethyl ether with β -(2:4-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaconic acid (1:1 mol.) in the presence of sulphuric acid (80%) according to Gogte's method and the subsequent demethylation of the product. This is not, however, successful. The reaction has been tried under different conditions and in the presence of different condensing agents but without success.

The direct synthesis is then attempted by condensing resorcin with 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (1:1 mol) in the presence of (1) sulphuric acid (75% and 100%), (2) phosphorus oxychloride, (3) phosphorus pentoxide, (4) aluminium chloride and (5) thionyl chloride as condensing agents. A small quantity of the dilactone has been obtained only in the reaction with phosphorus oxychloride. In all other cases, the 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid is recovered unchanged. It seems, therefore, that in the formation of the dilactone the reaction between acetone dicarboxylic acid and resorcin takes the course as shown in (i) and that the acetone dicarboxylic acid acts in the ketonic form. According to the literature available, the most satisfactory conditions for this type of reaction are to carry out the condensation at low temperature and under the influence of sulphuric acid (75%, Dixit and Gokhale, *loc. cit.*) and when resorcin is condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid under these conditions, the dilactone is obtained in fairly good quantity as compared with the 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid. This lends support to the course of the reaction represented in (i).

Further investigation of the non-acidic condensation product is being continued with a view to confirming its constitution and to studying some of its expected synthetical reactions. Work is also in progress for studying the use of new condensing agents like sulphuryl chloride, anhydrous zinc chloride, sodium ethoxide etc. for the condensation of phenols, naphthols and their ethers with acetone dicarboxylic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetone dicarboxylic Acid.—Anhydrous citric acid (50 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (90 c.c.) at 60-65° till the effervescence of carbon monoxide subsided. The mixture was then cooled and poured over crushed ice (about 160 g.) with stirring and kept in a cool place for 1 hour. A crystalline precipitate soon separated. It was filtered on flannel, washed with small quantities of ethyl acetate, dried on a porous plate and crystallised from ethyl acetate. It has to be preserved under vacuum in a desiccator, yield 75%, white needles, m.p. 136° (decomp.).

Condensation of Resorcin with Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid.

(a) *In the presence of Anhydrous Aluminium Chloride.*—Anhydrous aluminium chloride (27 g.) was added in small quantities to a fine suspension of acetone dicarboxylic acid (15 g.) and resorcin (11 g.) in dry carbon bisulphide (150 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about 4 hours with a condenser fitted with a calcium chloride guard tube. The carbon bisulphide was distilled off and the dry orange-coloured residue

was mixed with crushed ice (about 200 g.) containing a small quantity of hydrochloric acid. The white solid was filtered off, washed with water and then shaken with a solution of sodium bicarbonate (about 10%). A part of it dissolved and the solution was separated from the residue by filtration.

The filtrate on acidification gave 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid, in long shining white needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 203-204° (decomp.), yield 5.4 g.. Its alkaline solution shows a beautiful blue fluorescence (mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen). It was decarboxylated to 4-methylumbelliferone, m.p. 182°. (Found: C, 59.62; H, 3.90 per cent. Equiv., 219. Calc. for $C_{11}H_8O_3$: C, 59.72; H, 4.07 per cent. Equiv., 220).

The non-acidic residue was washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in prismatic crystals which blacken at 210° and melt at 290°, yield 6 g. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, methyl alcohol; sparingly soluble in water, benzene, petroleum ether and carbon tetrachloride. It gives a greenish colouration in alcoholic solution with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 64.96; H, 4.20. $C_{17}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 65.37; H, 3.84 per cent).

(b) *In the presence of Phosphorus Oxychloride.*—Phosphorus oxychloride (11 g.) was gradually added to a mixture of acetone dicarboxylic acid (5 g.) and resorcin (3.8 g.) in a flask fitted with an air condenser with a calcium chloride guard tube with constant shaking and cooling. It was then allowed to stand overnight and then poured over crushed ice (about 50 g.). The yellowish solid, which separated, was filtered, washed and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution as given under (a) to separate the acid 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (2.8 g.) and the dilactone (3.2 g.). Both of these were found identical with the corresponding substances obtained in (a).

(c) *In the presence of Phosphorus Pentoxide.*—To an intimate mixture of acetone dicarboxylic acid (15 g.) and resorcin (11 g.) phosphorus pentoxide (15 g.) was added in small quantities. The mixture soon melted to a viscous liquid and a vigorous reaction followed with liberation of heat. After the reaction subsided, the flask was fitted with a calcium chloride guard tube and heated on a water-bath at 75-80° for about 3 hours. The reaction mixture was mixed with crushed ice (about 50 g.). A semi-solid mass separated which on standing overnight changed to a powder from which 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (5 g.) and the dilactone (13 g.) were isolated by treatment with sodium bicarbonate according to the process given under (a).

(d) *In the presence of Thionyl Chloride.*—A mixture of thionyl chloride (5.5 c.c.) and dry benzene (10 c.c.) was gradually added to a solution of acetone dicarboxylic acid (15 g.) and resorcin (11 g.) in dry benzene (40 c.c.) in a flask through the condenser tube. The mixture became slightly warm due to the heat of the reaction and developed a blue-black colour. After keeping the reaction mixture for 24 hours the benzene layer was decanted off and the pinkish solid was mixed with crushed ice (about 50 g.). The white powder, which separated, was filtered, washed and separated by sodium carbonate into 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (3 g.) and the dilactone (7 g.) as mentioned under (a).

Hydrolysis of the Dilactone.

(a) *By Aqueous Alkali.*—The dilactone (2 g.) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (50 c.c. of 5%) for 2 hours. The mixture was cooled and acidified and the solid separating was filtered, washed and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution which dissolved most of it. This was filtered and the filtrate was then acidified. The acidic substance, which separated, was crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles (1 g.), m.p. 203° (decomp.). It was identified as 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid.

The filtrate after removing the solid product of hydrolysis was acidified and a brominating mixture containing potassium bromide and potassium bromate (100 c.c. of 0.4 *N*) was added to it in small quantities with good shaking after each addition. A reddish flocculent precipitate appeared in a short time. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as white silky needles, m.p. 110° (decomp.), yield 0.8 g. It was identified with a known specimen of 4 : 6-resorcin dibromide by mixed m.p. (Found : Br, 59.53. Calc. for $C_8H_4O_2Br_2$: Br, 59.68 per cent).

It was observed that bromination with a stronger brominating mixture (1 *N*) produced 2 : 4-dibromoresorcin as short needles, m.p. 92° instead of the 4 : 6-dibromo compound

(b) *By Alcoholic Sodium Hydroxide (5%).*—The dilactone (2 g.) was hydrolysed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (5%) according to the method described above. On removal of alcohol and acidification a white precipitate was obtained. This was identified as 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid. The filtrate on bromination gave 4 : 6-dibromoresorcin.

(c) *By Acid.*—The dilactone (2 g.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (50 c.c. of 75%) for about 2 hours. The mixture was cooled and poured on ice. The separated white powder was removed by filtration, washed and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution in which it dissolved and was precipitated by acid. White shining needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 202° (decomp.). It was identified as 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid by mixed m.p. and conversion into 4-methylumbelliferone. The filtrate on bromination gave 4 : 6-dibromoresorcin, m.p. 110°.

Hydrolysis and Methylation of the Dilactone.—A mixture of the dilactone (10 g.), methyl alcohol (80 c.c.) and sodium hydroxide solution (80 c.c. of 20%) was heated under reflux for a short time and cooled. Dimethyl sulphate (40 g.) was added gradually with occasional cooling. The mixture was then refluxed for 2 hours, and the reaction was completed by adding sodium hydroxide (30 c.c. of 20%) and heating it for about 30 minutes. On cooling, an oily layer separated. This was extracted by ether and the aqueous portion on acidification gave a white powder. This was filtered, washed and purified through its copper salt, yellowish white prismatic plates from alcohol, m.p. 169° (decomp.), yield 4 g.

This acid was identified with β -2 : 4-dimethoxyphenylglutaconic acid (m.p. 169-170° decomp.) which was prepared by condensing resorcin dimethyl ether with acetone dicarboxylic acid in the presence of phosphorous oxychloride as the condensing agent, according to Bawadekar (M.Sc. Thesis to the Bombay Univ., 1941). The identity of the acid was further confirmed by preparing its semi-anilide (m.p. 165°) and methyl

ester (m.p. 112°). (Found : C, 58.5; H, 5.16. Equiv. 132.05. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}O_6$: C, 58.64; H, 5.26 per cent. Equiv., 133.)

The dark liquid obtained from the ethereal extract was purified by distillation and was found identical with resorcin dimethyl ether, almost colourless liquid, b.p. 217°, yield 3.5 g. It was brominated by bromine in acetic acid and the product was crystallised from dilute alcohol as long pinkish needles, m.p. 139°. The dibromo derivative of resorcin dimethyl ether mentioned in literature has a m.p. 137-138°.

Attempted Methylation of the Dilactone.—The dilactone (2 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (10 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (6 g.) for 2 hours. After evaporation of the pyridine, the mixture was poured into ice-water, from which the original dilactone was recovered unchanged.

Acetylation of the Dilactone.—The acetyl derivative of the dilactone was prepared as usual using acetic anhydride and a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as flat white prisms, m.p. 186°. (Found : C, 63.52; H, 4.18. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 63.63; H, 4.04 per cent).

Benzoylation of the Dilactone.—The dilactone was benzoylated in pyridine solution with benzoyl chloride. It was crystallised from acetone as prismatic plates, m.p. 206°. (Found : C, 71.23; H, 3.74. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 71.50; H, 3.84 per cent).

When benzoylation was carried out in the presence of dilute sodium hydroxide another substance with a higher m.p. (260°) was obtained. This is suspected to be the *C*-benzoyl derivative. Its exact nature, however, is still under investigation.

Heating at m.p.—On heating the dilactone at its m.p. in a paraffin-bath for about 1 hour, a partially charred mass and a small quantity of white sublimate were obtained. The sublimate showed tests of resorcin and the charred mass on purification with animal charcoal yielded about 70% of the original substance.

Synthesis of the Dilactone from 7-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—Phosphorus oxychloride (10 g.) was slowly added to a mixture of 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (5 g.) and resorcin (3.5 g.) which was then kept for about 48 hours with shaking at intervals. It was then poured into ice (about 25 g.). The solid separating was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. Most of it dissolved leaving only a small quantity of non-acidic residue (0.5 g.). This was crystallised from alcohol in microscopic prismatic crystals, m.p. 290° (with charring at 210°). Its alcoholic solution turns greenish with ferric chloride. Its melting point was not depressed on mixing it with an equal quantity of the non-acidic substance obtained by condensing acetone dicarboxylic acid with resorcin described above.

Other condensing agents like phosphorous pentoxide, thionyl chloride, sulphuric acid (75%), and dry hydrochloric acid gas were tried with a view to improving the yield, but without success. Condensation of resorcin with the ethyl ester of 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid was tried in the presence of sodium ethoxide, but there was hardly any reaction.

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